

ACHIEVING GENDER EQUALITY IN PARLIAMENT: AN OVERVIEW OF THE PERFORMANCE OF THE 11th COMPOSITION (2024–2028) OF THE MACEDONIAN ASSEMBLY IN PLURALISM

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Abstract

Democracy and gender equality are closely interconnected and mutually constitutive concepts. Democratization, in itself, is not a guarantee of gender equality. In the twentieth century, one of the greatest democratic achievements worldwide was the increased inclusion of women in overall societal developments, including political life – primarily as voters, but also as elected representatives. In the decades that followed, the concept of Gender-Sensitive Parliaments (GSP) emerged as the clearest expression of parliamentary responsibility to promote and achieve gender equality. The idea of GSP has since been established as an international democratic normative framework.

The purpose of this paper is to analyze the current parliamentary composition of the Assembly of the Republic of North Macedonia (RNM), constituted after the parliamentary elections held on May 8, 2024, through the lens of a gender-sensitive parliament. The paper first provides a theoretical discussion of the concept itself, followed by an in-depth analysis of the current situation in the RNM. In its concluding section, the paper offers recommendations for the further advancement of the GSP concept and presents final observations. In general terms, it may be emphasized that over more than three decades of political pluralism, the Republic of North Macedonia has experienced a transition of women in parliament from being a “small minority” to a “large minority” – yet still far from equal representation.

Keywords: gender-sensitive parliaments, Macedonian Assembly, women’s representation, electoral law, gender quotas;

1. INTRODUCTION

Democracy, as a concept, is continuously subject to evaluation and re-evaluation. In the twentieth century, one of the greatest democratic achievements worldwide was the increased inclusion of women in overall social processes, including political life – primarily as voters, but also as elected representatives (IPU, 2012: 8). Women, on the one hand, increasingly managed to overcome barriers to their participation in parliaments. On the other hand, once they entered these institutions, they often faced additional difficulties and challenges (Commonwealth Parliamentary Association Study Group, 2001: 4).

Over time, this created the need for parliaments themselves to ensure “not only that everyone is properly represented in decision-making, but also that legislation and government actions take account of the needs, interests, and experiences of women and men

on an equal basis” (Johnson, 2022: 9). This aspect is crucial, as parliaments have historically been dominated and led by men, leaving a lasting imprint of masculine culture and traditions on these institutions (Rai and Spary, 2019). These factors gave rise to initiatives aimed at promoting gender equality within political institutions, including parliaments, where deeply rooted models of rules, norms, and everyday practices have made them particularly resistant to change (Erikson and Freidenvall, 2023).

Hence, individual actions and political “goodwill,” accumulated over time through numerous efforts to embed changes within the rules, practices, and “organizational memory” of these institutions (ibid.), resulted in a greater number of women entering parliaments as “a legitimate aspiration of the citizenry in order to obtain a larger measure of justice and advancement in the democratization of political power” (Bernabeuand Rodríguez Gustá, 2013:4).

Over the past quarter-century, in response to these challenges, international organizations, practitioners, and academics have developed and advocated the concept of Gender-Sensitive Parliaments (GSP) (OSCE/ODIHR, 2021: 7). In the decades that followed, “the concept of ‘gender-sensitive parliaments’ (GSP) has become the clearest expression of parliaments’ responsibility to promote and achieve gender equality” (ibid., 14).

The aim of this paper is to analyze the current parliamentary composition of the Assembly of the Republic of North Macedonia (RNM), constituted after the parliamentary elections held on May 8, 2024, through the lens of a gender-sensitive parliament. The paper is structured as follows: it first presents a theoretical discussion of the concept itself, followed by an analysis of the current situation in the RNM, and concludes with specific recommendations for further advancement and key findings.

2. GENDER-SENSITIVE PARLIAMENT – DEFINING THE CONCEPT

As noted in the introductory section, the concept of Gender-Sensitive Parliaments (GSP) increasingly appears as an emerging international norm that, according to Palmieri and Baker (2022), nevertheless requires “localization”. Its origins “can be traced to the 2001 report by the Commonwealth Parliamentary Associations’ study group, entitled *Gender Sensitizing Commonwealth Parliaments*” (Ahrens, Erzeel and Fieremans, 2024:3).

The most basic definition of a gender-sensitive parliament describes it as an institution that “actively respects and delivers on gender equality” (OSCE/ODIHR, 2022: 3). However, one of the most frequently cited and widely used definitions of GSP was provided by the Inter-Parliamentary Union (IPU), which defines a GSP as “parliaments whose organization, operations, methods, and work resemble the needs and interests of men and women, which remove obstacles (material, structural, and/or cultural) to the equal participation of women, ensure resources for promoting gender equality, and offer a positive example and model to the society in general” (Kvinna, 2020: 3).

The same definition emphasizes that a GSP is a modern parliament because it “deals and reflects the demands of contemporary society for equality and non-discrimination, is aware that internal regulations and norms are not gender neutral, and makes efforts to achieve gender equality both internally and externally, through the adoption and promotion of gender sensitive policies” (ibid.).

Over time, the need has arisen for a revised and updated definition of GSP– one that is comprehensive yet more concrete, concise, and focused than the original IPU definition, which at first glance appears somewhat lengthy and extensive. In this context, the definition proposed by Childs and Palmieri (2023: 177) has gained prominence. They define GSP as a parliament that “values and prioritizes gender equality as a social, economic, and political

objective, and reorients and transforms their institutional culture, practice, and outputs towards those objectives”.

The following section therefore offers an overview of the actions that parliaments should undertake to strengthen the GSP concept, highlighting internal cultural, structural, and procedural – both formal and informal – aspects aimed at advancing gender sensitivity and achieving gender equality (OSCE/ODIHR, 2021: 15).

3. GENDER POLICIES IN PARLIAMENTS

For decades, women’s rights and gender equality have represented essential global, democratic, and social norms. They have been promoted through a series of international agreements, among which the most significant are: the 1979 Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW); the Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action (1995); United Nations Security Council Resolution 1325 on Women, Peace and Security; and Sustainable Development Goal 5 (SDG 5) adopted in 2015 (see: Inter Pares, 2024: 30).

In 2022, the Inter-Parliamentary Union (IPU), in its report *Women in Parliament*, marked a historic milestone by declaring that “not a single functioning parliament in the world is male-only” (IPU, 2023: 1–2).

This success can be attributed to the clearly defined gender policies implemented across numerous parliaments worldwide through strategic visions and action plans that enabled the achievement of concrete objectives. However, such measures alone would have remained insufficient without the establishment of self-assessment mechanisms capable of identifying existing gaps, emerging challenges, and providing adequate solutions for overcoming them (OECD, 2023: 96).

At their core, parliaments are complex institutions, and many aspects of their work directly influence gender sensitivity. Scholarly literature on this topic emphasizes that such sensitivity is particularly visible in what is often referred to as the “sacred parliamentary trinity” – *representation*, *legislation*, and *oversight* (OSCE/ODIHR, 2022: 7).

Regarding *representation*, also known in the literature as *descriptive representation*,²⁰ the focus is placed on ensuring gender balance in leadership positions across all parliamentary committees and delegations (OSCE/ODIHR 2021: 8). When it comes to *legislation*, gender-sensitive practices remain limited. The existence of international mechanisms and national legal frameworks that affirm equality before the law, prohibit discrimination, and encourage inclusivity are, by themselves, insufficient. Far greater significance lies in a legislative process that anticipates gender equality concerns, ensuring that existing governance rules and social structures do not perpetuate gender discrimination (OSCE/ODIHR, 2022: 8). As for *gender-sensitive oversight*, it encompasses a wide range of dimensions but can be concretized through monitoring progress; placing gender issues on the political agenda; and exploring the actual impact of government policies, programmes and actions (Inter Pares, 2024: 107).

Based on these principles, the following section presents an analysis of the current parliamentary composition of the Assembly of the Republic of North Macedonia (2024–2028) through the lens of gender sensitivity.

²⁰ The research in this area has focused not only on the *descriptive* representation of women in parliaments (their numerical representation) but also on *substantive* representation (how women’s interests are addressed) and *symbolic* representation, such as how they appear in the media and other forms of communication (Pàrlamaid na h-Alba, 2023: 7).

4. THE CURRENT 11TH PARLIAMENTARY COMPOSITION IN PLURALISM: A GENDER-SENSITIVE ANALYSIS

On the occasion of the 30th anniversary of ODIHR (the primary institution of the OSCE), marked in 2021, its study *Realizing Gender Equality in Parliament: A Guide for Parliaments in the OSCE Region* demonstrated that parliaments in OSCE participating states, including North Macedonia, can generally boast strong female representation, “ranging from near parity to a little less than 15%. In fact, the OSCE regional average (29.6%) is higher than the global average (25%)” (OSCE/ODIHR, 2021: 16).

In the current Assembly (2024–2028), there are 47 women MPs out of 120, representing 39.1% of the total membership. It should be noted that this constitutes an increase from the initial composition following the May 8, 2024 elections, which included 41 women MPs (34.1%). This growth is a logical outcome of the appointment of MPs to the new government, as well as subsequent resignations of members who assumed other posts and functions. From the governing coalitions of VMRO-DPMNE and VLEN, an additional 7 and 3 women MPs, respectively, entered the Assembly. Of the 10 VMRO-DPMNE MPs who joined the executive branch, 2 were women. Their parliamentary seats were filled by the next 2 female candidates from the same party list, in accordance with Article 153-a of the Electoral Code, which stipulates that: “if the Member of Parliament whose term of office has been terminated on one of the grounds prescribed in Article 152 of this Code is female, then the next female candidate on the list shall become a Member of Parliament for the remaining duration of the term of office”. This legal provision “ensures stability in the number of women in the Assembly” (Donev, 2023:5). In cases where MPs resigned, their replacements were determined according to the party and electoral district list order.

When analyzing the Assembly from a gender-sensitive perspective, particular attention should be paid to key parliamentary leadership positions, such as the Speaker and the Secretary General (the head of parliamentary administration). Regarding the Speaker’s position, the trend of exclusively male officeholders has continued. Since the introduction of the pluralist system, only once – during 1984–1985 – has a woman served as Speaker. In the current composition, there is one female Deputy Speaker out of 3, which represents an improvement, considering that in the 1990s none of the three parliamentary convocations had a female Deputy Speaker. The same situation was observed in the previous parliamentary composition (2020–2024), as well as in the 5th composition in pluralism (2006–2008). Conversely, a positive development is the reappointment of a woman as Secretary General of the Assembly, as was also the case in the previous term. Over more three decades of political pluralism, a total of 3 women have held this position. These figures are consistent with global trends within OSCE member states, where “in both cases, men were more likely to hold the positions of speaker (65%) and secretary general (64%)” (OSCE/ODIHR, 2021: 25).

A gender-sensitive parliament has always attached great significance to the selection of MPs as chairs, members, and deputy members of various parliamentary structures, such as committees and delegations. In these cases it is important “that women are present in a more diverse range” (ibid., 28). In the current parliamentary composition (2024–2028), there are 10 active parliamentary delegations. In two of them, gender parity is observed; in five, women are in the majority; in two, men dominate; and in one, there are no women at all. It

is noteworthy, however, that women outnumber men in delegation leadership positions by a ratio of 6 to 4.²¹

Table 1. Gender Representation in the Parliamentary Delegations

Beyond delegations, many parliaments worldwide have committees that function as “gendered institutional spaces”, which are manifested through their leadership and membership” (Inter Pares, 2024: 93). In this regard, the situation in the Assembly of North Macedonia differs somewhat from that of delegations. Of the 24 committees, men dominate in 15, while women lead in 7; 2 committees exhibit gender parity. Only 6 committees are chaired by women, compared to 16 chaired by men, and women serve as deputy chairs in 8 committees. In 7 committees, women represent less than 25% of members, whereas in 3 committees they form an overwhelming majority (around 80%).

The Committee on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men, established in 2006 under the Law on Equality of Women and Men,²² traditionally shows the highest female representation. In this parliamentary term, the Verification Committee also follows this trend, as do “committees that encompass the sphere of the everyday life of women” (Jovevska Ćorĝevik and Janeska, 2020: 15) – Education, Science and Sport (78%), Culture and Tourism (62%), and Social Policy, Demography and Youth (56%), among others. With 52% female representation, the Committee on European Affairs likewise continues its tradition of female predominance.

Conversely, in the 11th parliamentary term, committees in which women are traditionally underrepresented have once again come to the fore. These include those overseeing the Implementation of the Measures for Interception of Communications (100% men); the Work of the National Security Agency and the Intelligence Agency (78%); Agriculture, Forestry, and Water Resources Management (77%); and Defense and Security (72%) (ibid., 13-14).

²¹ All data presented in this paper are current as of October 1, 2025, and are taken from the official website of the Assembly of the Republic of North Macedonia; they reflect the presentation provided there.

²² “Since its establishment, the average representation of women in this committee has been over 65%, and so far, all chairpersons and deputy chairpersons of this committee have been women” (Jovevska Ćorĝevik and Janeska, 2020: 15).

This demonstrates the persistent absence of women in committees stereotypically perceived as “male”, where they effectively hold “a reduced capacity to act within these domains, meaning that decisions are made by their male colleagues” (ibid.,4).

Table 2. Gender Representation in the Working Bodies of the Assembly of the Republic of North Macedonia

Working Bodies of the Assembly of the Republic of North Macedonia	mb.²³	f	%	m	%	ch.
Committee on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men	22	18	82%	4	18%	f
Committee on Oversight of the Implementation of the Measures for Interception of Communications	8	0	0%	8	100%	m
Committee on Election and Appointment Issues	26	12	46%	14	54%	m
Committee on Rules of Procedure, and Mandatory-Immunity Issues	18	2	11%	16	89%	m
Committee on Oversight of the Work of the National Security Agency and the Intelligence Agency	18	4	22%	14	78%	m
Committee on European Affairs	29	15	52%	14	48%	m
Finance and Budget Committee	29	10	34%	19	66%	f
Committee on Economic Affairs, Labor and Energy Policy	22	6	27%	16	73%	m
Committee on Monitoring the Appropriate and Fair Representation of Citizens Belonging to All Communities	25	6	24%	19	76%	m
Committee on Agriculture, Forestry and Water Resources Management	22	5	23%	17	77%	m
Inter-Community Relations Committee	18	7	39%	11	61%	/
Committee on Transport, Digital Transformation, Environment and Spatial Planning	22	3	14%	19	86%	m
Committee on Social Policy, Demography and Youth	25	14	56%	11	44%	/
Standing Inquiry Committee for Protection of Civil Rights and Freedoms	29	9	31%	20	69%	m
Committee on Culture and Tourism	21	13	62%	8	38%	f
Verification Committee	5	4	80%	1	20%	f
Committee on Local Self-Government	26	5	19%	21	81%	m
Committee on Health Care	22	11	50%	11	50%	f
Committee on Foreign Policy and Foreign Trade	26	14	54%	12	46%	m
Committee on Education, Science and Sport	28	22	78%	6	22%	f

²³The regular members, as well as their deputies, have also been taken into consideration.

Committee on Constitutional Issues	34	16	47%	18	53%	m
Legislative Committee	28	14	50%	14	50%	m
Committee on Defense and Security	25	7	28%	18	72%	m
Committee on the Political System and Inter-Ethnic Relations	30	12	40%	18	60%	m

These data from North Macedonia’s 11th parliamentary composition reinforce the broader global observation that the number and proportion of women across party groups are automatically reflected in the composition of parliament’s committees (Inter Pares, 2024: 94). To overcome such a situation, authors such as Erikson and Josefson (2023) advocate for additional efforts aimed at achieving equal representation of both genders. This can be accomplished even through informal procedures that strive for fair representation of women. However, the Assembly of the Republic of North Macedonia, in its previous composition, adopted a more formalized approach: with the 2023 amendments to Article 114(3) of its Rules of Procedure, it decided that, during the selection of the Assembly’s working bodies, permanent delegations, and parliamentary cooperation groups, a gender-balanced composition should be ensured (in accordance with the current percentage of female MPs in the ongoing mandate).

Moreover, as Donev (2023: 7) notes, “apart from their participation in committees, the presence of female MPs in other structures of the Assembly as decision-makers is also crucial. For this reason, it is essential that women more frequently assume the role of parliamentary group coordinators and take part in coordination meetings where the Assembly’s agenda is determined”. In the 2024–2028 term, the Assembly comprises 6 parliamentary groups, corresponding to the number of political formations represented. According to parliamentary rules, a group must consist of at least 5 MPs. No parliamentary group is currently coordinated by a woman. However, except for the political movement ZNAM and the political party Levica, the remaining 4 groups each have both a male and a female deputy coordinator, and VMRO-DPMNE includes one male and two female deputy coordinators.

Most parliaments promote the concept of gender equality and women’s empowerment not only through formal bodies (such as the Committee on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men in the Macedonian case) but also through informal groups, such as the Women’s Parliamentary Club (see: Sawyer 2020, 2023). The Women’s Parliamentary Club has a long tradition in Macedonian parliamentarism, having been established in 2003, three years prior to the founding of the Committee on Equal Opportunities. Both bodies are crucial for achieving the aims outlined in the previous chapter – namely, to play a central role in gender-sensitive lawmaking and oversight. In the case of North Macedonia, “The Club, supported by the civil sector and the international community, made the most significant contribution to improving the normative framework regulating the nomination and election of Members of Parliament in the Assembly” (Jovevska Ćorĝevik and Janeska, 2020: 16) and “played a significant role in the fight for gender equality and the participation of women in politics” (Donev, 2023: 8).

The gender-sensitive dimension of each parliamentary composition is largely determined by the manner in which the candidate lists are submitted. In the respective elections, a total of 17 electoral lists were submitted – by 16 political parties and coalitions, as well as one group of voters. Of these, only 6 entered the 11th parliamentary composition in pluralism. The analysis therefore focuses on the structure of their electoral lists from a gender perspective. It should be emphasized that since 2015, the Electoral Code has

stipulated that political parties are obliged to submit candidate lists with at least 40% female representation. Among the parliamentary parties in this composition, the coalition led by SDSM offered the highest female representation (49%), while the Levica party, across all 6 electoral districts, opted for the legal minimum of 40% women – 8 female candidates per list. The VMRO-DPMNE-led coalition adopted the same strategy in 5 out of 6 electoral districts, as did the Albanian coalitions VLEN and the one led by DUI in 4 out of 6 electoral districts.

Table 3. The Percentage of Women on the Electoral Lists of the Parliamentary Represented Parties in the Current Parliamentary Composition (2024-2028)

Political party	ED ₁ ²⁴	ED ₂	ED ₃	ED ₄	ED ₅	ED ₆	Total %
VMRO DPMNE	40%	40%	40%	40%	40%	60%	43%
SDSM	55%	45%	50%	55%	40%	50%	49%
ZNAM	40%	40%	40%	50%	45%	50%	44%
Levica	40%	40%	40%	40%	40%	40%	40%
VLEN	40%	50%	40%	40%	50%	40%	43%
DUI	40%	40%	45%	45%	40%	40%	41%

However, a higher percentage of women on candidate lists does not automatically translate into greater female parliamentary representation, since women are often placed in non-electable positions merely to fulfill the legal quota. Consequently, we cannot expect substantial change as long as parties formally comply with legal provisions without improving women’s placement on the lists (Donev, 2023: 13). This can be illustrated with a concrete example: On the lists of VMRO-DPMNE, Levica, and ZNAM, there was only one female lead candidate. In contrast, the two Albanian coalitions that entered the Assembly did not have a single woman in the first position. The SDSM coalition was the most innovative, introducing the concept of a lead and co-lead candidate by positioning the male candidate in the first position on the list in the 1st, 4th, and 5th electoral districts, and the female candidate in the 3rd and 6th. All of these lead candidates were accompanied by a co-leader of the opposite gender, placed in the second position on the list.

Thus, it can be concluded that with nearly 40% women in the current parliamentary composition (precisely 39.1%), the Republic of North Macedonia is a regional leader in women’s parliamentary participation. This case reaffirms the argument that a proportional electoral system combined with a well-calibrated gender quota can significantly improve female representation in the legislature. The proportional model is often seen as “more responsive to societal gender norms for equality and demands for various reasons” (Inter Pares, 2024: 52). However, not every proportional system is equally favorable – only those operating with large multi-member districts, which allow the election of multiple candidates, tend to be effective. This is precisely the case in North Macedonia, which is divided into 6 constituencies with 20 seats each. In contrast, single-member districts typical of majoritarian systems allow for only one winner (Matland, 2005). This model can be particularly unfavorable for women, as shown by Macedonia’s early 1990s experience, when the two-round majoritarian system produced only 4% women MPs in 1990 and 3% in 1994, partly due to the low nomination rates of 6% and 8% women, respectively (Jovevska ĆorĆevik and Janeska, 2020: 9-10). However, this runoff model (*ballotage*), historically associated with

²⁴ Electoral district.

France as the most paradigmatic example, produces 39.5% female representation in the French National Assembly, since the model there is combined with a gender quota (Inter Pares, 2024: 53).

The effects of gender quotas are well studied in literature – they are most effective when they “are binding, use a quota percentage close to 50%, apply rank-order rules specifying the distribution of men and women on candidate lists or in winnable constituencies, and demand strict sanctions that do not rely solely on financial penalties” (Dahlerup 2016; Krook 2009 quoted in Inter Pares, 2024: 57). The Electoral Code of North Macedonia anticipates many of these provisions, setting the quota at 40% and stipulating that “at least one out of every three places shall be reserved for the underrepresented sex, with at least one additional place out of every ten places” (Art. 64 (5) Electoral Law of the R. of N. Macedonia).

5. CONCLUSION

Through the introduction of proportional representation in 2002 and the continued and permanent interventions in electoral legislation aimed at improving the gender quota,²⁵ the Republic of North Macedonia has dramatically enhanced women’s representation in its legislative body. Over more than three decades of political pluralism, the observation made by Dahlerup (2016: 64) also applies to North Macedonia – that “women in parliaments have moved from being a ‘small minority’ to a ‘large minority’”.

The proposed *Action Plan for the Advancement of Equality between Women and Men in the Assembly of the Republic of North Macedonia 2025–2027*, adopted by the Committee on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men in its current composition (2024–2028), reaffirms several commitments included in the previous two plans (2020–21; 2022–24), many of which remain unfulfilled. Nonetheless, the report notes certain achievements compared to previous periods. The Assembly has incorporated several aspects of gender equality strengthening into its Rules of Procedure. To raise awareness about promoting gender equality, an annual plenary session dedicated to this topic has been institutionalized. Multiple trainings and workshops have been conducted to strengthen capacities for recognizing and preventing violence against women in politics. Additionally, within the Office of the Secretary General, a Gender Equality Advisor position has been established (see: Assembly of RNM, 2025: 3, 18).

This third and current Action Plan reaffirms the commitment to lobby for amendments to the Electoral Code introducing a 50% gender quota through a “zipper system”, ensuring equality between women and men on candidate lists for both parliamentary and local council elections. The report concludes that no changes have yet been made to the legal framework and that intra-party dialogue regarding the promotion of women in executive and local government positions (i.e., the introduction of quotas) remains difficult. It also notes the absence of developed and implemented guidelines for the use of gender-sensitive language in parliamentary work.

Nevertheless, hope remains that the current parliamentary composition will address these challenges and continue advancing the concept of the Gender-Sensitive Parliament (GSP) within the Assembly of the Republic of North Macedonia.

²⁵ The initial quota was set at 30%, and with the amendments to the Electoral Code in 2015, it was raised to 40%. In 2006, the quota was further specified to ensure that for every three positions, one must be allocated to the less represented gender.

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